

FORWARD – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

WP7 _ Deliverable 7.1

Common monitoring and evaluation system and database of monitoring indicators

Project Acronym	FORWARD
Project name	Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
Grant agreement n°	824550
Project type	Coordination and Support action
Start date - End Date	01/01/2019 - 31/12/2021
Workpackage	WP7
Deliverable	DEL 7.1
Responsible partner	Nexa
Contributors	
Delivery date	2019/11/29

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

Table of contents

ABOUT FORWARD	3A - WHY FORWARD ?
3B - THE SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE FORWARD PROJECT :	3C - THE ACTIVITIES :
4METHODOLOGY FOR PROJECT MONITORING AND EVALUATION	5A - OBJECTIVES
5B - EVALUATION TYPOLOGIES	5C - MONITORING AND EVALUATION PLAN
12ANNEXES	13
INDICATORS FORESEEN IN THE PROPOSAL	14
DASHBOARD ARCHITECTURE	15
OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT ACTIVITIES REPORTS & THE DASHBOARD	Erreur ! Le signet n'est pas défini.

I - About FORWARD

A - Why Forward ?

The FORWARD project is a European Coordination and Support Action funded under a H2020 Swafs2018-2020 call, that has been awarded with 4.2 million euros for a duration of 3 years. The aim of the project is to support outermost regions of Europe to improve their research excellence and build their capacities to increase their participation in current and future European research programmes. **FORWARD H2020** project is the opportunity to map the capabilities of the ORs in their fields of research experience and, on this basis, select potential European and international partners who can further strengthen their capacity. The project will also help to design the future EU research framework programme, helping ORs to reinforce their effective participation in it.

The project involves **24 partners** from **the nine European Outermost Regions (ORs): Guadeloupe, French Guiana, Martinique, Saint-Martin, Réunion, Mayotte, the Canary Islands, the Azores and Madeira**. The project addresses the issue of innovation in the ORs and the role they can play as laboratories for experimenting with innovative solutions, taking advantage of their potential.

B - The specific objectives of the FORWARD project :

Based on a multi-actor, multidisciplinary and cross-sectorial approach, the project aims at facilitating the collaboration and networking among representatives of the quadruple helix (university, SMEs, government, civil society) at regional level, between ORs, and with their counterparts from EU Members States and Third Countries at international level.

With that in mind, the project identifies several specific objectives:

1. To map outermost regions' ecosystems in research and innovation to underline strengths, weaknesses and potentials for growth for each OR;
2. To identify actual and future fields of excellence and competitive advantages of the different regions and define emerging specialization areas for each OR and define ORs' friendly topics in the future Framework Programmes;
3. To characterize and objective barriers to ORs participation in H2020;
4. To accompany the transformation and capacity building of each OR research and innovation ecosystem to better exploit these potentials, by improving their excellence (in research, technical / technological development, uptake of research results, entrepreneurship discovery, collaboration and multidisciplinary approaches, administrative procedures and frameworks, policy impact and science) and the mobilization of multiple kind of stakeholders (research organization, companies, public authorities and civil society organizations) through a quadruple helix approach;
5. To support the formulation of participatory and research-based action plans with long-term perspective;
6. To increase the regional, national, European and worldwide visibility and recognition of outermost regions research capacities and activities in their fields of specialization;

7. To encourage the constitution of critical research mass in ORs through networking, exchanges and consortia with regional, national, European and global research centers;
8. To design and experiment effective tools to overcome existing barriers and support the implication of ORs in Horizon 2020 and future framework;
9. To foster socio-economic development of the European ORs through the quadruple helix approach;
10. To foster ORs geographical integration within the European Union and towards Third Countries.

C - The activities :

The FORWARD project is organized in three logical phases to reach the above described objectives. The first phase aims at updating the regional diagnostics of the research and innovation regional ecosystems in the focus of regional RIS3 strategies, and of the specific needs of research and innovation actors in each OR for an enhanced participation in H2020, and future research programmes. This diagnosis also includes the assessment of the situation in Continental Europe. Such an analysis has led to the definition of joint strategy for the ORs to improve, promote and support their R&I ecosystems for the participation of the EU Framework Programmes and building the basis for training, networking, capacity building, communication activities.

The second phase would focus on building the needed capacities and structures to unlock their research potential and foster the participation of ORs in the Research Framework Programmes. The second phase represent the bulk of project activities and include the establishment of thematic working groups, the organization of capacity building activities as well as of dedicated networking and cooperation actions with other EU and Third Countries.

The third phase would rather focus on strengthening the connection between research and policy making in order to support the further development of smart specialization strategies in the ORs, identify research priorities of ORs with a view to the future Research Programmes and ensure the sustainability and impact of project results on a long term.

The project will be composed of eight work packages.

- 1 - Management and coordination
- 2 - Diagnostics of ORs' R&I ecosystems
- 3 - Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans
- 4 - Capacity building and training activities
- 5 - Networking activities
- 6 - Connecting research and policy making: next generation policy tools
- 7 - Monitoring, evaluation and performance
- 8 - Dissemination and communication

Methodology for project monitoring and evaluation

The Workpackage n°7 aims at impartially monitoring and evaluating the progress made by the project on OR's research potential and participation in Research Framework Programmes. To do so, Nexa is in charge of developing a methodology and provide guidelines to ensure a coherent approach among all partners (Task 7.1), and CDM is responsible for the analysis (Task 7.2 and 7.3).

A - Objectives

Monitoring and evaluation are important part of any project. Without these dimensions, measuring the success of a project and understanding why and how the project has reached or not its objectives are impossible. This methodology aims at evaluating the impacts of the project, through measuring the direct outputs of each WP and the progress made by OR in terms of R&I performance and participation in FP.

PROJECT EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

B - Evaluation typologies

2 types of evaluation are planned :

- Monitoring and assessment of the project activities
- Evaluation of the progress in FP participation and regional system

1) Project activities monitoring and assessment

Activities and results will be monitored for each WP. Moreover, the rationale behind the achievement of the project results will be investigated.

The following workpackages will be monitored¹ :

- WP2 - Diagnostics of ORs' R&I ecosystems
- WP3 - Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans
- WP4 - Capacity building and training activities
- WP5 - Networking activities
- WP6 - Connecting research and policy making: next generation policy tools
- WP7 - Monitoring and evaluation
- WP8 - Dissemination and communication

For each of them, three types of indicators will be collected :

- indicators of implementation, which allow partners to see if the activities described in the GA were implemented in each region and/or globally ;
- indicators of results, which indicate if the activities have reached the objectives that were foreseen;
- indicators of satisfaction, which, as mentioned in the GA, consist in feedbacks from the R&I community in each OR and help understanding how and why the results have been (or not) attained ;

The following tables describe the indicators in details :

	Objectives	Indicators
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping of OR ecosystem and potentials - Objectivization of barriers to FP participation - Formulation of participatory actions plan 	<p>Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of unique respondents to the surveys for the regional diagnosis and action plans - Number of participants to workshops organised for the regional diagnosis and action plans - Number of interviews organised for the regional diagnosis and action plans <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of diagnosis performed - Rate of planned actions that have been engaged since the actions plan adoption - Influence of the joint strategy on the regional actions plan and the WP implementation <p>Satisfaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction rate of regional contributors to the diagnosis and action plan on the WP2 implementation

	Objectives	Indicators

¹ WP1 activities and impacts are monitored by the Monitoring plan with the Deliverable 1.3

3	- Define ORs friendly topics for future FP	Implementation
		Results
		Satisfaction

	Objectives	Indicators
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement a Common Capacity Plan that take into account a multilevel & cross-sectorial approach and adjust it to the specific needs and the maturity of the OR R&I ecosystem, already identified in WP2 - Support and follow the OR's implementation of the capacity building Plan on the R&I ecosystem 	<p>Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development - Number of workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation - Number of trainings on scientific excellence in research - Number of trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation - Number of researchers attending trainings abroad - Number of R&I actors participating in the capacity actions - Number of regional meetings for MoU's preparation <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of the MoU - Level of achievement of the quantitative objectives - Increased number of stakeholders aiming at participating in FP <p>Satisfaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction rate of participants of the trainings and capacity building activities

	Objectives	Indicators
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Constitute critical research mass in ORs through networking, exchanges and consortia with regional, national, European and global research centers - Increase the geographical integration of OR within the European Union and towards Third Countries 	<p>Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of organized and participation in networking and brokerage events. - Number of short-term oriented networking activities. - Number of long-term oriented networking activities. <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of R&D proposals under development linked to networking activities. - Number of new scientific partnership agreements linked to Networking activities. - Number of new Research/ Industry collaborations linked to networking activities. <p>Satisfaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction rate of participants to mobilities

	Objectives	Indicators
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate the dialogue between the research community and policy makers, at regional, national and EU level 8. - To design and experiment effective tools to overcome existing barriers and support the implication of ORs in Horizon 2020 and future framework; 	<p>Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of events targeting policy makers in each region - Number of common event - Number of policy-making stakeholders having received policy briefs <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Level of achievement of the quantitative objectives - Number of public policy tools in research and innovation using FORWARD results at regional, national and EU level - Number of "new" participants in events (capture) <p>Satisfaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Event participant satisfaction measured by the average global rate obtained in qualitative satisfaction survey - Attendees regularity/ loyalty measured by the nr. of "recurring" participants is an indirect indicator of participant satisfaction

	Objectives	Indicators
7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impartially monitoring and evaluating the progress made by the project 	<p>Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compliance with the monitoring and evaluation plan - Number of respondents to satisfaction surveys / interviews <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of the progress <p>Satisfaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction rate of the WP leaders and regional delegates on the monitoring process impacts - Satisfaction rate of the project partners about the project implementation - Satisfaction rate of the advisory board members about activities involving the board

	Objectives	Indicators
8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase the regional, national, European and worldwide visibility and recognition of outermost regions research capacities and activities in their fields of specialization; 	<p>Implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of Forward event participation - Number of press release <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of press coverage (regional, national, european) about Forward - Number of OR's collaboration with other partners further to Forward participation to events <p>Satisfaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction rate of participants in Forward events (satisfactory questionnaire survey) given during forward events or downloaded on Forward website) - Knowledge rate about R & I in Outermost regions (situation at year 0 and situation at the end of Forward project)

2) Progress evaluation

Based on the results and experience acquired during the implementation of WP2 diagnosis, 2 sets of indicators are identified :

- indicators for FP participation
- indicators for R&I performance

a) FP participation indicators

For each outermost regions, the following indicators will be determined :

Indicator	Time frame	Update	Source
Number of FP projects	per year, from 2007 to 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Total number of FP projects over the programming	T0 = Total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Number of FP participations	per year, from 2007 to 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Total number of FP participations over the programming	T0 = Total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Number of proposals	T0 = Total amount up to July 2019	once a year	Regional delegate
Total EU contribution to the region	T0 = Total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Average share of the EU contribution granted to the region	T0 = share in July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Total number of projects per pillar (1, 2, 3)	T0 = total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Total number of projects per funding schemes	T0 = total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Total number of participating organizations over the programming	T0 = total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Total number of projects coordinated by the region (excluding monobeneficiaries)	T0 = total amount up to July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
% of EU contribution to the region per type of organizations (HES, REC, PUB, OTH, PRC)	T0 = % in July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
% of participation per type of organizations (HES, REC, PUB, PTH, PRC)	T0 = % in July 2019	once a year	CORDIS + revision by regional delegate
Share of EU contribution granted to the regional organisation having the highest number of participation	T0 = % in July 2019	once a year	Regionale delegate
Number and share of projects involving a partner from a neighbouring country	T0 = % in July 2019	once a year	Regional delegate
Number and share of projects involving an other OR	T0 = % in July 2019	once a year	Regional delegate
Total EU contribution to the	T0 = total amount up to July 2019	once a year	Nexa

region per capita per year of FP programming			
Ratio total EU contribution per capita per year / total R&I ESIF per capita per year	T0 = ratio in July 2019	once a year	Nexa
Ratio number of projects / number of researchers according to Eurostats	T0 = ratio in July 2019	once a year	Nexa
Decile group for total EU contribution (compared to NUTS2 regions)	T0 = decile group in 2019	once a year	Nexa
Decile group for total EU contribution per capita per year (compared to NUTS2 regions)	T0 = decile group	once a year	Nexa

b) R&I system indicators

Indicator	Time frame	Update	Source
Population	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Employment rate	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
GDP	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
GDP growth rate	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
GERD	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Patent applications to the European patent office	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
HRST	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
HRST % PA	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Students enrolled in tertiary education	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Tertiary education 24-64	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Tertiary education 30-34	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
PhD students	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
PhD intensity	T0 = 2019	Every year	Calculation by Nexa
Researchers	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
R&D personnel as % of the employment	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Number of researchers and R&D personnel	since 2009	Every year	Eurostats
Tertiary education attainment			
Number of foreign PhD students	T0 = 2019	Every year	Regional delegate

Number of post docs	T0 = 2019	Every year	Regional delegate
Number of foreign post docs	T0 = 2019	Every year	Regional delegate
Share of foreign PhD students	T0 = 2019	Every year	Regional delegate
Share of foreign post docs	T0 = 2019	Every year	Regional delegate
Net EU contribution per capita per year	T0 = 2019	Every year	Nexa
Total Research & Innovation ESIF per capita per year	T0 = 2019	Every year	Nexa

C - Monitoring and evaluation plan

The monitoring and evaluation plan is composed of :

- 8 reporting template, one by WP, to monitor project activities ;
 - each WP leader is responsible for collecting the data and analysing the results with the help of regional delegates;
- a dashboard for FP participation and regional system monitoring updated by Nexa with the help of the regional delegates;
- two reports (intermediary and final) elaborated by CDM.

1) Monitoring plan for project activities

For each WP, a dedicated reporting template is provided and accessible on the googledrive in the WP7 folder. Once a year (M17, M29), an update of the WP indicators is foreseen. Each WP leader provides CDM a report including updated indicators for WP activities and a synthetic analysis of the results/outcomes of their WP.

To ensure an efficient methodology based on common standards for satisfaction collection, WP leaders submit for validation by CDM the methodology they plan to implement, at least five weeks before each deadline. When satisfaction measurements target local R&I community members, WP leaders shall involve the regional delegates in the elaboration and implementation of the methodology.

2) Monitoring plan for OR progress

From the data collected by partners during the WP2, Nexa has built a dashboard on the OR participation in FP and their R&I system. This dashboard is available online on the OR platform. Once a year (M17, M29), an update of the dashboard will be published online by Nexa.

To do so, 4 weeks before each deadline, Nexa collects updated information from cordis database and eurostats. This information is sent to regional delegates who are responsible for completing (some data requires regional delegate intervention such as Share of EU contribution

granted to the regional organisation having the highest number of participation) and checking the data, within two weeks. Nexa then publishes the updated dashboard on line and sent it to CDM.

3) Analysis and reports

Based on the project activities reports and data from the dashboard, CDM elaborates, at Month 18 (intermediary) and Month 30 (final), reports analysing the progress made by OR and the impacts of the project on FP participation and regional R&I system. These report are submitted to the steering committee and advisory board members for revision. Once revised, the reports are submitted to the general assembly. As foreseen in the Grant agreement, the final report is submitted to the EC.

4) Calendar

	Who is responsible	2020												2021											
		M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Coordination, analysis & reports production	CDM																								
1. Process supervision	CDM																								
1. Elaboration and transmission of the intermediary report	CDM						M18																		
2. Elaboration and transmission of the final report (DEL 7.2)	CDM																	M30						update of the report	
Project activities monitoring and assessment	CDM																								
1. Satisfaction collection	WP leaders					M17											M29								
2. Other indicators collection	WP leaders					M17											M29								
3. Outcomes analysis and transmission to CDM	WP leaders					M17	M18	M19									M29	M30	M31						
FP participation updates	CDM																								
1. Cordis updates and transmission to regional delegates	Nexa					M17											M29								
2. Correction and validation	Regional delegates					M17	M18										M29	M30							
3. Transmission to CDM & publication	Nexa																								
Regional system updates	CDM																								
1. Eurostats updates and transmission to regional delegates	Nexa					M17											M29								
2. Other indicators	Regional delegates					M17	M18										M29	M30							
3. Transmission to CDM & publication	Regional delegates																								

Annexes

A - Indicators foreseen in the proposal

INDICATORS PER WP		AZO	CAN	GUA	GUY	MAD	MAR	MAY	REU	SAI
WP2	Number of Workshops organized	2	2	3	2	2	1	1	3	1
	Average number of participants to the workshops	30	50	30	30	50	20	20	50	20
	Number of interviews carried out	10	50	20	10	10	5	5	20	5
	Average number of respondents to the survey	50	100	50	20	50	20	20	50	15
WP4	Number of trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1
	Number of workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3	3	3	2	2	0	1	3	0
	Number of trainings on scientific excellence in research	3	5	3	2	1	0	0	2	0
	Number of trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	1
	Number of researchers attending trainings abroad	5	10	7	20	20	6	0	10	0
	Number of R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	20	62	60	5	20	3	2	30	2
	Number of regional meetings for MoU's preparation	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
	Number of networking events organised	3	10	3	1	2	1	1	3	1
WP5	Short mobilities for researchers	3	15	7	3	20	1	1	10	1
	Long mobilities for researchers	3	8	3	3	0	0	0	3	0
WP6	Number of events targeting policy makers	3	2	3	2	3	3	1	3	1
WP7	Average number of institutions annually consulted for activity report	10	50	20	10	20	10	5	20	5
	Number of respondents to surveys	10	80	50	10	20	10	5	50	5
	Number of respondents to interviews	10	30	20	10	20	10	5	20	5

B - Dashboard architecture

C - Reporting templates

The reporting templates are available online on the Forward google drive (WP7).